

THE COLLATZ CONJECTURE
Order and harmony in the sequence numbers

by

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Abstract: I propose a numerical table that demonstrates visually that the sequences formed with Collatz's algorithm always reach 1.

Keywords: Collatz Conjecture, $3n+1$ problem, number theory.

Introduction: The conjecture was raised by the mathematician Lothar Collatz in 1937. It is also known as other names: The $3n + 1$ problem, the Ulam conjecture, the Kakutani problem, the conjecture of Thwaites, the Hasse algorithm or the Syracuse problem.

The conjecture reads as follows:

- 1 - Any natural number is chosen, n .
- 2 - If it is even divide by 2, $(n / 2)$.
- 3 - If odd, multiply by 3 and add 1 to the result, $(3n + 1)$.

The process is repeated with each result and a sequence is obtained that always ends in 1 and always It is so, whatever the initial number. The unknown is why it happens and if it happens with all natural numbers.

Overview: For the Collatz conjecture, I identify two types of odd numbers: Those of the form $4n + 3$ and those of the $4n + 1$ form.

Applying $(3m + 1) / 2$ to those of the form $4n + 3$, an odd number is found that is greater than the previous one and the sequence is ascending.

Applying the same operation to those of the $4n + 1$ form, it is an even number that requires more divisions by 2, so the odd number they arrive at is always smaller than the previous one and the sequence is descending.

A sequence of Collatz will be more or less descending and more or less long as obtained more or less odd numbers of the form $4n + 1$.

If in the set of odd numbers there are the same number of both, do they have the same probability of going out in the Collatz sequences? Can you predict how many will there be and at what moment the numbers of the form $4n + 1$ will appear and the sequence will descend?

I also identify two types of even numbers: Those of the form $4n + 2$ and those of the form $4n + 4$. Those of the form $4n + 2$ admit a single division $n / 2$ and the odd number that results is greater than the previous one and the sequence is ascending.

Those of the form $4n + 4$ admit two or more divisions $n / 2$ and the odd number they arrive at is smaller than the previous one and the sequence is descending.

The amount of numbers in each column is always the same, depending on the value of k:

	n	valor de k											cantidad de números por columna
2k-1	0	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	...	0 impares rojos, 1 número impar verde y un número par	
2(2k-1)	1	2	6	10	14	18	22	26	30	34	...	1 número impar rojo, 1 número impar verde y un número par	
4(2k-1)	2	4	12	20	28	36	44	52	60	68	...	2 números impares rojos, 1 número impar verde y un número par	
8(2k-1)	3	8	24	40	56	72	88	104	120	136	...	3 números impares rojos, 1 número impar verde y un número par	
16(2k-1)	4	16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240	272	...	4 números impares rojos, 1 número impar verde y un número par	
32(2k-1)	5	32	96	160	224	288	352	416	480	544	...	5 números impares rojos, 1 número impar verde y un número par	
64(2k-1)	6	64	192	320	448	576	704	832	960	1088	...	6 números impares rojos, 1 número impar verde y un número par	
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	

In each of the columns $k = 2^n * (2k-1)$ there are n odd red numbers, one last green odd number and the even number that closes the column.

Example: in column $k = 2^{50}$ there are 50 red odd numbers, the first is number 2251799813685247 and the 50th is 957197316922470118360331 and the last odd of the column, which is green, is number 1435795975383705177540497. The even number that closes The column is 2153693963075557766310746. In Annex 1, the sequence development started with this first column number.

They will also have the same amount of numbers each of the columns $k = (2k-1) * 2^{50}$.

A sequence obtained with the Collatz conjecture algorithm is formed by an indeterminate number of columns in the table or cycles.

A sequence started with the first odd number of any column $k = (2k-1) * 2^{1000000}$ would have in that column, 1000000 odd red, one last green odd and an even number closing the column. There will be the same odd number in all columns, for every value of $(2k-1)$.

If the sequence were started with a power number of 2 close to infinity, the first column of the table or cycle of that sequence would have that same amount of odd numbers.

The table is infinite but all its columns or cycles are bounded geometric progressions.

The same columns without the odd ones of the form $4n + 3$:

k	14	16	61	46	52	88	223	84	142	160	456	289	217	163	31	12	3	1
n																		
0			121				445					577	433	325	61		5	1
1	41		182	137			668		425			866	650	488	92		8	2
2	62			206	233			377	638							53		
3					350	593		566			3077					80		
4		161				890					4616							
5		242								2429								
6									3644									
7																		
8																		

The odd green ones followed by the even number at the end of each column k (even) are also in the columns k (odd).

K	21	81	61	69	117	297	223	189	213	1215	1539	289	217	163	31	27	3	1
	41	161	121	137	233	593	445	377	425	2429	3077	577	433	325	61	53	5	1
	62	242	182	206	350	890	668	566	638	3644	4616	866	650	488	92	80	8	2

Equivalence of k even and K odd : $k(3/2)^n = K$ Example: $k160(3/2)^5 = K1215$

At each repetition of the algorithm operation $(3m + 1) / 2$, applied to the first odd number of the column, the sequence “jumps” from one column to another, leaving it at a single step to reach the even number that can be divided at least 2^2 . This will always occur in any sequence until the green odd is in row n (0).

An example of the evolution of the columns of the table in which “loses” an odd number in each jump, $k * 3/2$:

$$32 * 3/2 = 48, 48 * 3/2 = 72, 72 * 3/2 = 108, 108 * 3/2 = 162 \text{ y } 162 * 3/2 = 243 \qquad 32 * (3/2)^5 = 243$$

$$k = 32, K = 243$$

k	32	48	72	108	162	243
n						
0	63	95	143	215	323	485
1	95	143	215	323	485	728
2	143	215	323	485	728	
3	215	323	485	728		
4	323	485	728			
5	485	728				
6	728					
7						

Column k (32) contains the odd numbers and an even number of a Collatz sequence from number 63 to number 728, occupying rows n (0) through n (6).

The same numbers are in columns k (32), k (48), k (72), k (108), k (162) and k (243), occupying row n (0), because in a sequence there may be the numbers of any of these columns and not necessarily all of them.

The cycle that follows the previous one is that of the column of the number 91, because $728/2^3 = 91$

k	46	69
n		
0	91	137
1	137	206
2	206	
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		

The next cycle: $206/2 = 103$

k	52	78	117
n			
0	103	155	233
1	155	233	350
2	233	350	
3	350		
4			
5			
6			
7			

The triangle T(4):

4											
9	14										
19	29	44									
39	59	89	134								
79	119	179	269	404							
159	239	359	539	809	1214						
319	479	719	1079	1619	2429	3644					
639	959	1439	2159	3239	4859	7289	10934				
1279	1919	2879	4319	6479	9719	14579	21869	32804			
2559	3839	5759	8639	12959	19439	29159	43739	65609	98414		
5119	7679	11519	17279	25919	38879	58319	87479	131219	196829	295244	
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...

The triangle T(6):

6											
13	20										
27	41	62									
55	83	125	188								
111	167	251	377	566							
223	335	503	755	1133	1700						
447	671	1007	1511	2267	3401	5102					
895	1343	2015	3023	4535	6803	10205	15308				
1791	2687	4031	6047	9071	13607	20411	30617	45926			
3583	5375	8063	12095	18143	27215	40823	61235	91853	137780		
7167	10751	16127	24191	36287	54431	81647	122471	183707	275561	413342	
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...

The triangle T (n) that contains the first odd number of the Collatz sequence is what will be the beginning or first cycle of it.

In the columns of the table and in the rows of the triangles, the numbers:
 $a(n + 1) = (a(n) * 3 + 1) / 2$.

MULTIPLY BY 3 AND DIVIDE BETWEEN 2

If in triangle T (0) I add 1 to their numbers, another triangle T (1) results:

1											
2	3										
4	6	9									
8	12	18	27								
16	24	36	54	81							
32	48	72	108	162	243						
64	96	144	216	324	486	729					
128	192	288	432	648	972	1458	2187				
256	384	576	864	1296	1944	2916	4374	6561			
512	768	1152	1728	2592	3888	5832	8748	13122	19683		
1024	1536	2304	3456	5184	7776	11664	17496	26244	39366	59049	
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...

In each column of this triangle, the even numbers of the sequences and the odd numbers they reach after being subjected to n divisions by 2, which coincide with the columns in the table of even numbers.

A triangle T (n) for each value of $(n) = 1, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 25, \dots (6n-1, 6n + 1)$ and we can write on them all even numbers.

In the rows of the triangle, each number: $a(n + 1) = a(n) * 3/2$. All have as prime factors 3 and 2.

Multiplying by 3 and dividing by 2 is the script with which a sequence obtained with the Collatz algorithm is developed and this keeps the odd ones in the sequence in the same row.

Example: $8 * 3 = 24, 24/2 = 12, 12 * 3 = 36, 36/2 = 18, 18 * 3 = 54, 54/2 = 27$. (numbers 7, 11, 17, 26 of the sequence).

To develop a sequence of Collatz in this triangle and to see its entire route, from its beginning until it reaches 1, we form a table with the triangle as a base.

Starting with each last number of the rows of the triangle, we apply these two operations: To the odd we add 1 and to the even we divide it by 2.

We write each result above the previous one, in the same column, until we reach 1.

In this extension of the triangle, the numbers are in red.

														1	1	...	
													1	1	2	2	...
												1	2	2	3	4	...
									1	1	2	3	4	5	7	...	
						1	1	2	2	3	5	7	10	14	...		
					1	2	2	3	4	6	9	13	19	28	...		
			1	1	2	3	4	5	8	11	17	25	37	55	...		
		1	1	2	2	3	5	7	10	15	22	33	49	73	110	...	
	1	2	2	3	4	6	9	13	20	29	44	65	98	146	219	...	
1	2	3	4	6	8	12	18	26	39	58	87	130	195	292	438	...	
2	3	5	7	11	16	23	35	52	77	116	173	260	390	584	876	...	
4	6	9	14	21	31	46	69	103	154	231	346	519	779	1168	1752	...	
8	12	18	27	41	61	92	137	206	308	462	692	1038	1557	2336	3504	...	
16	24	36	54	81	122	183	274	411	616	923	1384	2076	3114	4671	7007	...	
32	48	72	108	162	243	365	547	821	1231	1846	2768	4152	6228	9342	14013	...	
64	96	144	216	324	486	729	1094	1641	2461	3691	5536	8304	12456	18684	28026	...	
128	192	288	432	648	972	1458	2187	3281	4921	7382	11072	16608	24912	37367	56051	...	
256	384	576	864	1296	1944	2916	4374	6561	9842	14763	22144	33216	49823	74734	112101	...	
512	768	1152	1728	2592	3888	5832	8748	13122	19683	29525	44287	66431	99646	149468	224202	...	
1024	1536	2304	3456	5184	7776	11664	17496	26244	39366	59049	88574	132861	199291	298936	448404	...	
2048	3072	4608	6912	10368	15552	23328	34992	52488	78732	118098	177147	265721	398581	597872	896807	...	
4096	6144	9216	13824	20736	31104	46656	69984	104976	157464	236196	354294	531441	797162	1195743	1793614	...	
8192	12288	18432	27648	41472	62208	93312	139968	209952	314928	472392	708588	1062882	1594323	2391485	3587227	...	
16384	24576	36864	55296	82944	124416	186624	279936	419904	629856	944784	1417176	2125764	3188646	4782969	7174454	...	
32768	49152	73728	110592	165888	248832	373248	559872	839808	1259712	1889568	2834352	4251528	6377292	9565938	14348907	...	
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	

In this table we can visualize any sequence of Collatz, whose first odd number of it, is in the triangle. If it is not, it can be displayed in the table whose base or triangle contains that number. All sequences started with the odd numbers of a triangle row will have the same trajectory.

Like the triangles, the tables obtained from them, are unique for each $T(n)$ and the representation of the sequences will be made in the table formed from the triangle that contains the first odd number of the same.

For example, to visualize the sequence started with the number 508, whose first odd number is 127, we will represent it in the table of triangle $T(1)$, because in row 2^8 there is the number 127.

The development of a Collatz sequence started with the number 39:

												...	
										1	1	...	
								1	1	2	2	...	
								1	2	2	3	4	...
					1	1	2	3	4	5	7	...	
			1	1	2	2	3	5	7	10	14	...	
		1	2	2	3	4	6	9	13	19	28	...	
1	1	2	3	4	5	8	11	17	25	37	55	...	
2	2	3	5	7	10	15	22	33	49	73	109	...	
3	4	6	9	13	19	29	43	65	97	145	217	...	
5	8	12	17	26	38	57	86	129	193	289	433	...	
10	15	23	34	51	76	114	171	257	385	577	865	...	
20	30	45	68	102	152	228	342	513	769	1154	1730	...	
40	60	90	135	203	304	456	684	1026	1538	2307	3460	...	
80	120	180	270	405	608	912	1367	2051	3076	4614	6920	...	
160	240	360	540	810	1215	1823	2734	4101	6151	9227	13840	...	
320	480	720	1080	1620	2430	3645	5468	8202	12302	18453	27680	...	
640	960	1440	2160	3240	4860	7290	10935	16403	24604	36906	55359	...	
1280	1920	2880	4320	6480	9720	14580	21870	32805	49208	73812	110717	...	
2560	3840	5760	8640	12960	19440	29160	43740	65610	98415	147623	221434	...	
5120	7680	11520	17280	25920	38880	58320	87480	131220	196830	295245	442868	...	
10240	15360	23040	34560	51840	77760	116640	174960	262440	393660	590490	885735	...	
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	

The sequence obtained with the Collatz algorithm, started with the number 39:

39, 118, 59, 178, 89, 268, 134, 67, 202, 101, 304, 152, 76, 38, 19, 58, 29, 88, 44, 22, 11, 34, 17, 52, 26, 13, 40, 20, 10, 5, 16, 8, 4, 2, 1.

The sequence runs through the table developed from triangle T (5), because the first odd number in the sequence, 39, is in this triangle. The sequences started with the numbers 59, 89 and 134 will have the same route.

For triangle extension numbers, (in red), if 1 is subtracted from the odd number instead of adding 1, the table is equally valid:

Impar-1

11								1	
10							1	2	
9				1	1	2	4		
8			1	2	3	5	8		
7		1	1	2	4	6	10	16	
6	1	2	3	5	8	13	20		
5	3	4	7	11	17	26	40		
4	6	9	14	22	34	52			
3	12	19	29	44					
2	25	38	58	88					
1	51	77	116						
0		154	232						
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

Impar+1

11							1	1	
10					1	1	2	2	
9				1	2	2	3	4	
8		1	1	2	3	4	5	8	
7	1	2	2	3	5	7	10	16	
6	2	3	4	6	9	13	20		
5	4	5	8	11	17	26	40		
4	7	10	15	22	34	52			
3	13	20	29	44					
2	26	39	58	88					
1	51	77	116						
0		154	232						
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

103																			
206	309																		
412	618	927																	
824	1236	1854	2781																
1648	2472	3708	5562	8343															
3296	4944	7416	11124	16686	25029														
...	...	...	...	...	...	...													

205, 308

13																			
26	39																		
52	78	117																	
104	156	234	351																
208	312	468	702	1053															
416	624	936	1404	2106	3159														
...	...	...	...	...	...	...													

77, 116

5																			
10	15																		
20	30	45																	
40	60	90	135																
80	120	180	270	405															
160	240	360	540	810	1215														
...	...	...	...	...	...	...													

29, 44

1																			
2	3																		
4	6	9																	
8	12	18	27																
16	24	36	54	81															
32	48	72	108	162	243														
...	...	...	...	...	...	...													

11, 17, 26

7																			
14	21																		
28	42	63																	
56	84	126	189																
112	168	252	378	567															
224	336	504	756	1134	1701														
...	...	...	...	...	...	...													

13, 20

1																			
2	3																		
4	6	9																	
8	12	18	27																
16	24	36	54	81															
32	48	72	108	162	243														
...	...	...	...	...	...	...													

5, 8

The sequence started with the number 27 in the 18 columns of the table or cycles:

k	14	16	61	46	52	88	223	84	142	160	456	289	217	163	31	12	3	1	
n																			
0	27	31	121	91	103	175	445	167	283	319	911	577	433	325	61	23	5	1	
1	41	47	182	137	155	263	668	251	425	479	1367	866	650	488	92	35	8	2	
	62	71		206	233	395		377	638	719	2051					53			
3		107			350	593		566		1079	3077					80			
4		161				890				1619	4616								
5		242								2429									
6										3644									
7																			
8																			
9																			

The same sequence in the table of triangles:

The sequence started with the number 27 has 82 horizontal iterations of the odd numbers and 29 vertical iterations of the even numbers.

We also see the development of the sequence with the columns of the odd number table, such as rows of triangles:

The rows of the triangles that form the cycles of the sequence, with the odd ones of the $4n + 3$ form in red, the odd ones of the $4n + 1$ form of green and the even numbers that join the cycles in yellow.

In the following table, a sequence started with the number 31:

28
27
26
25
24
23
22
21
20
19
18
17
16
15
14
13
12
11
10
9
8
7
6
5
4
3
2
1
0

Applying $(3m + 1) / 2$ to an odd number causes the sequence to move to the next column of the table, but in the same row and ascends to higher rows when at the end of each cycle, the even number is divided by 2. In this table, ascending means approaching number 1.

In the table, each cycle or triangle is above the previous one and the sequence never descends to a lower row. Neither will it go parallel to the line of numbers 1 nor will it be separated, because the cycles or columns with the largest number of odd numbers (longer rows) are very scarce:

In the first 10,000 columns, the one with the largest amount of odd numbers is column $k(8192)$, with 14 numbers. It is followed by column $k(4096)$ with 13 numbers, two columns have 12 numbers, five columns have 11 numbers, ten columns with 10 numbers, twenty columns with 9 numbers, etc.

In the first 50,000, the column with the most numbers $k(32768)$ has 16.

In the first 300,000, the column with the most numbers $k(262144)$ has 19.

In the first 1,000,000, the column with the most numbers $k(524288)$ has 20.

All the rows of the triangles or columns in the table are finite and their last number is even, so it will inevitably end in a number 1.

It is a visual demonstration that, although the numbers suffer increasing and decreasing oscillations, all sequences will ascend to number 1.

THE AMOUNT OF ODD NUMBERS in each column of the odd table and the amount of even numbers in the even table: 1, 2, 1, 3, 1, 2, 1, 4, 1, 2, . . . matches the number of digits 1 to the right of the last 0 in the binary representation of the odd numbers and the number of digits 0 to the right of the last 1 in the binary representation of the even numbers. Example:

1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21
1	11	101	111	1001	1011	1101	1111	10001	10011	10101
2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	20	22
10	100	110	1000	1010	1100	1110	10000	10010	10100	10110
1	2	1	3	1	2	1	4	1	2	1

The last row corresponds to the amount of numbers in the columns of the tables and forms a fractal sequence with infinite sequences of the natural numbers, as follows: The numbers 1 are in the values of odd k and the following terms are in $2k$.

Example: The terms of the first sequence are in $k(1), k(2), k(4), k(8), k(16), . . .$

The terms of the second sequence are in $k(3), k(6), k(12), k(24), k(48), . . .$

The terms of the third sequence are in $k(5), k(10), k(20), k(40), k(80), . . .$

k	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	...																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																			
1	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	33	35	37	39	41	43	45	47	49	51	53	55	57	59	61	63	65	67	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	...																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																			
2	5	8	11	14	17	20	23	26	29	32	35	38	41	44	47	50	53	56	59	62	65	68	71	74	77	80	83	86	89	92	95	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128	131	134	137	140	143	146	149	152	155	158	161	164	167	170	173	176	179	182	185	188	...																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																				
3	8	17	26	35	44	53	62	71	80	89	98	107	116	125	134	143	152	161	170	179	188	197	206	215	224	233	242	251	260	269	278	287	296	305	314	323	332	341	350	359	368	377	386	395	404	413	422	431	440	449	458	467	476	485	494	503	512	521	530	539	548	557	566	575	584	593	602	611	620	629	638	647	656	665	674	683	692	701	710	719	728	737	746	755	764	773	782	791	800	809	818	827	836	845	854	863	872	881	890	899	908	917	926	935	944	953	962	971	980	989	998	1007	1016	1025	1034	1043	1052	1061	1070	1079	1088	1097	1106	1115	1124	1133	1142	1151	1160	1169	1178	1187	1196	1205	1214	1223	1232	1241	1250	1259	1268	1277	1286	1295	1304	1313	1322	1331	1340	1349	1358	1367	1376	1385	1394	1403	1412	1421	1430	1439	1448	1457	1466	1475	1484	1493	1502	1511	1520	1529	1538	1547	1556	1565	1574	1583	1592	1601	1610	1619	1628	1637	1646	1655	1664	1673	1682	1691	1700	1709	1718	1727	1736	1745	1754	1763	1772	1781	1790	1799	1808	1817	1826	1835	1844	1853	1862	1871	1880	1889	1898	1907	1916	1925	1934	1943	1952	1961	1970	1979	1988	1997	2006	2015	2024	2033	2042	2051	2060	2069	2078	2087	2096	2105	2114	2123	2132	2141	2150	2159	2168	2177	2186	2195	2204	2213	2222	2231	2240	2249	2258	2267	2276	2285	2294	2303	2312	2321	2330	2339	2348	2357	2366	2375	2384	2393	2402	2411	2420	2429	2438	2447	2456	2465	2474	2483	2492	2501	2510	2519	2528	2537	2546	2555	2564	2573	2582	2591	2600	2609	2618	2627	2636	2645	2654	2663	2672	2681	2690	2699	2708	2717	2726	2735	2744	2753	2762	2771	2780	2789	2798	2807	2816	2825	2834	2843	2852	2861	2870	2879	2888	2897	2906	2915	2924	2933	2942	2951	2960	2969	2978	2987	2996	3005	3014	3023	3032	3041	3050	3059	3068	3077	3086	3095	3104	3113	3122	3131	3140	3149	3158	3167	3176	3185	3194	3203	3212	3221	3230	3239	3248	3257	3266	3275	3284	3293	3302	3311	3320	3329	3338	3347	3356	3365	3374	3383	3392	3401	3410	3419	3428	3437	3446	3455	3464	3473	3482	3491	3500	3509	3518	3527	3536	3545	3554	3563	3572	3581	3590	3599	3608	3617	3626	3635	3644	3653	3662	3671	3680	3689	3698	3707	3716	3725	3734	3743	3752	3761	3770	3779	3788	3797	3806	3815	3824	3833	3842	3851	3860	3869	3878	3887	3896	3905	3914	3923	3932	3941	3950	3959	3968	3977	3986	3995	4004	4013	4022	4031	4040	4049	4058	4067	4076	4085	4094	4103	4112	4121	4130	4139	4148	4157	4166	4175	4184	4193	4202	4211	4220	4229	4238	4247	4256	4265	4274	4283	4292	4301	4310	4319	4328	4337	4346	4355	4364	4373	4382	4391	4400	4409	4418	4427	4436	4445	4454	4463	4472	4481	4490	4499	4508	4517	4526	4535	4544	4553	4562	4571	4580	4589	4598	4607	4616	4625	4634	4643	4652	4661	4670	4679	4688	4697	4706	4715	4724	4733	4742	4751	4760	4769	4778	4787	4796	4805	4814	4823	4832	4841	4850	4859	4868	4877	4886	4895	4904	4913	4922	4931	4940	4949	4958	4967	4976	4985	4994	5003	5012	5021	5030	5039	5048	5057	5066	5075	5084	5093	5102	5111	5120	5129	5138	5147	5156	5165	5174	5183	5192	5201	5210	5219	5228	5237	5246	5255	5264	5273	5282	5291	5300	5309	5318	5327	5336	5345	5354	5363	5372	5381	5390	5399	5408	5417	5426	5435	5444	5453	5462	5471	5480	5489	5498	5507	5516	5525	5534	5543	5552	5561	5570	5579	5588	5597	5606	5615	5624	5633	5642	5651	5660	5669	5678	5687	5696	5705	5714	5723	5732	5741	5750	5759	5768	5777	5786	5795	5804	5813	5822	5831	5840	5849	5858	5867	5876	5885	5894	5903	5912	5921	5930	5939	5948	5957	5966	5975	5984	5993	6002	6011	6020	6029	6038	6047	6056	6065	6074	6083	6092	6101	6110	6119	6128	6137	6146	6155	6164	6173	6182	6191	6200	6209	6218	6227	6236	6245	6254	6263	6272	6281	6290	6299	6308	6317	6326	6335	6344	6353	6362	6371	6380	6389	6398	6407	6416	6425	6434	6443	6452	6461	6470	6479	6488	6497	6506	6515	6524	6533	6542	6551	6560	6569	6578	6587	6596	6605	6614	6623	6632	6641	6650	6659	6668	6677	6686	6695	6704	6713	6722	6731	6740	6749	6758	6767	6776	6785	6794	6803	6812	6821	6830	6839	6848	6857	6866	6875	6884	6893	6902	6911	6920	6929	6938	6947	6956	6965	6974	6983	6992	7001	7010	7019	7028	7037	7046	7055	7064	7073	7082	7091	7100	7109	7118	7127	7136	7145	7154	7163	7172	7181	7190	7199	7208	7217	7226	7235	7244	7253	7262	7271	7280	7289	7298	7307	7316	7325	7334	7343	7352	7361	7370	7379	7388	7397	7406	7415	7424	7433	7442	7451	7460	7469	7478	7487	7496	7505	7514	7523	7532	7541	7550	7559	7568	7577	7586	7595	7604	7613	7622	7631	7640	7649	7658	7667	7676	7685	7694	7703	7712	7721	7730	7739	7748	7757	7766	7775	7784	7793	7802	7811	7820	7829	7838	7847	7856	7865	7874	7883	7892	7901	7910	7919	7928	7937	7946	7955	7964	7973	7982	7991	8000	8009	8018	8027	8036	8045	8054	8063	8072	8081	8090	8099	8108	8117	8126	8135	8144	8153	8162	8171	8180	8189	8198	8207	8216	8225	8234	8243	8252	8261	8270	8279	8288	8297	8306	8315	8324	8333	8342	8351	8360	8369	8378	8387	8396	8405	8414	8423	8432	8441	8450	8459	8468	8477	8486	8495	8504	8513	8522	8531	8540	8549	8558	8567	8576	8585	8594	8603	8612	8621	8630	8639	8648	8657	8666	8675	8684	8693	8702	8711	8720	8729	8738	8747	8756	8765	8774	8783	8792	8801	8810	8819	8828	8837	8846	8855	8864	8873	8882	8891	8900	8909	8918	8927	8936	8945	8954	8963	8972	8981	8990	8999	9008	9017	9026	9035	9044	9053	9062	9071	9080	9089	9098	9107	9116	9125	9134	9143	9152	9161	9170	9179	9188	9197	9206	9215	9224	9233	9242	9251	9260	9269	9278	9287	9296	9305	9314	9323	9332	9341	9350	9359	9368	9377	9386	9395	9404	9413	9422	9431	9440	9449	9458	9467	9476	9485	9494	9503	9512	9521	9530	9539	9548	9557	9566	9575	9584	9593	9602	9611	9620	9629	9638	9647	9656	9665	9674	9683	9692	9701	9710	9719	9728	9737	9746	9755	9764	9773	9782	9791	9800	9809	9818	9827	9836	9845	9854	9863	9872	9881	9890	9899	9908	9917	9926	9935	9944	9953	9962	9971	9980	9989	9998	10007	10016	10025	10034	10043	10052	10061	10070	10079	10088	10097	10106	10115	10124	10133	10142	10151	10160	10169	10178	10187	10196	10205	10214	10223	10232	10241	10250	10259	10268	10277	10286	10295	10304	10313	10322	10331	10340	10349	10358	10367	10376	10385	10394	10403	10412	10421	10430	10439	10448	10457	10466	10475	10484	10493	10502	10511	10520	10529	10538	10547	10556	10565	10574	10583	10592	10601	10610	10619	10628	10637	10646	10655	10664	10673	10682	10691	10700	10709	10718	10727	10736	10745	10754	10763	10772	10781	10790	10799	10808	10817	10826	10835	10844	10853	10862	10871	10880	10889	10898	10907	10916	10925	10934	10943	10952	10961	109

Example:

- T(1) $2 * T(0) + 1 = 1$ odd number.
- T(2) $2 * T(1) + 2 = 4$ odd numbers and the even 8.
- T(3) $2 * T(2) + 3 = 11$ odd numbers and the even 26.
- T(4) $2 * T(3) + 4 = 26$ odd numbers and the even 80.
- T(5) $2 * T(4) + 5 = 57$ odd numbers and the even 242.
- T(6) $2 * T(5) + 6 = 120$ odd numbers and the even 728.
- T(7) ...

APPENDIX 1

Sequence started with the number 2251799813685247, which is the first number in column k (2^{50}) of the table.

In this column are the first 50 odd ones of the sequence, which are of the form $4n-1$ and occupy the even steps from 0 to 98. The odd 51° , which is of the form $4n-3$ in step 100 and the pair 52° which is the last number of the column, in step 102.

step: value

0: 2251799813685247
1: 6755399441055742
2: 3377699720527871
3: 10133099161583614
4: 5066549580791807
5: 15199648742375422
6: 7599824371187711
7: 22799473113563134
8: 11399736556781567
9: 34199209670344702
10: 17099604835172351
11: 51298814505517054
12: 25649407252758527
13: 76948221758275582
14: 38474110879137791
15: 115422332637413374
16: 57711166318706687
17: 173133498956120062
18: 86566749478060031
19: 259700248434180094
20: 129850124217090047
21: 389550372651270142
22: 194775186325635071
23: 584325558976905214
24: 292162779488452607
25: 876488338465357822
26: 438244169232678911
27: 1314732507698036734
28: 657366253849018367
29: 1972098761547055102
30: 986049380773527551
31: 2958148142320582654
32: 1479074071160291327
33: 4437222213480873982
34: 2218611106740436991
35: 6655833320221310974
36: 3327916660110655487
37: 9983749980331966462
38: 4991874990165983231
39: 14975624970497949694
40: 7487812485248974847
41: 22463437455746924542
42: 1123171827873462271
43: 33695156183620386814
44: 16847578091810193407
45: 50542734275430580222
46: 25271367137715290111
47: 75814101413145870334
48: 37907050706572935167
49: 113721152119718805502
50: 56860576059859402751

51: 170581728179578208254
52: 85290864089789104127
53: 255872592269367312382
54: 127936296134683656191
55: 383808888404050968574
56: 191904444202025484287
57: 575713332606076452862
58: 287856666303038226431
59: 863569998909114679294
60: 431784999454557339647
61: 1295354998363672018942
62: 647677499181836009471
63: 1943032497545508028414
64: 971516248772754014207
65: 2914548746318262042622
66: 1457274373159131021311
67: 4371823119477393063934
68: 2185911559738696531967
69: 6557734679216089595902
70: 3278867339608044797951
71: 9836602018824134393854
72: 4918301009412067196927
73: 14754903028236201590782
74: 7377451514118100795391
75: 22132354542354302386174
76: 11066177271177151193087
77: 33198531813531453579262
78: 16599265906765726789631
79: 49797797720297180368894
80: 24898898860148590184447
81: 74696696580445770553342
82: 37348348290222885276671
83: 112045044870668655830014
84: 56022522435334327915007
85: 168067567306002983745022
86: 84033783653001491872511
87: 252101350959004475617534
88: 126050675479502237808767
89: 378152026438506713426302
90: 189076013219253356713151
91: 567228039657760070139454
92: 283614019828880035069727
93: 850842059486640105209182
94: 425421029743320052604591
95: 1276263089229960157813774
96: 638131544614980078906887
97: 1914394633844940236720662
98: 957197316922470118360331
99: 2871591950767410355080994
100: 1435795975383705177540497
101: 4307387926151115532621492
102: 2153693963075557766310746
103: 1076846981537778883155373
104: 3230540944613336649466120
105: 1615270472306668324733060
106: 807635236153334162366530
107: 403817618076667081183265
108: 1211452854230001243549796
109: 605726427115000621774898
110: 302863213557500310887449
111: 908589640672500932662348
112: 454294820336250466331174
113: 227147410168125233165587
114: 681442230504375699496762

115: 340721115252187849748381
116: 1022163345756563549245144
117: 511081672878281774622572
118: 255540836439140887311286
119: 127770418219570443655643
120: 383311254658711330966930
121: 191655627329355665483465
122: 574966881988066996450396
123: 287483440994033498225198
124: 143741720497016749112599
125: 431225161491050247337798
126: 215612580745525123668899
127: 646837742236575371006698
128: 323418871118287685503349
129: 970256613354863056510048
130: 485128306677431528255024
131: 242564153338715764127512
132: 121282076669357882063756
133: 60641038334678941031878
134: 30320519167339470515939
135: 90961557502018411547818
136: 45480778751009205773909
137: 136442336253027617321728
138: 68221168126513808660864
139: 34110584063256904330432
140: 17055292031628452165216
141: 8527646015814226082608
142: 4263823007907113041304
143: 2131911503953556520652
144: 1065955751976778260326
145: 532977875988389130163
146: 1598933627965167390490
147: 799466813982583695245
148: 2398400441947751085736
149: 1199200220973875542868
150: 599600110486937771434
151: 299800055243468885717
152: 899400165730406657152
153: 449700082865203328576
154: 224850041432601664288
155: 112425020716300832144
156: 56212510358150416072
157: 28106255179075208036
158: 14053127589537604018
159: 7026563794768802009
160: 21079691384306406028
161: 10539845692153203014
162: 5269922846076601507
163: 15809768538229804522
164: 7904884269114902261
165: 23714652807344706784
166: 11857326403672353392
167: 5928663201836176696
168: 2964331600918088348
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170: 741082900229522087
171: 2223248700688566262
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193: 890303633130962114
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195: 1335455449696443172
196: 667727724848221586
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203: 1126790535681373930
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218: 44565445991304341
219: 133696337973913024
220: 66848168986956512
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222: 16712042246739128
223: 8356021123369564
224: 4178010561684782
225: 2089005280842391
226: 6267015842527174
227: 3133507921263587
228: 9400523763790762
229: 4700261881895381
230: 14100785645686144
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233: 1762598205710768
234: 881299102855384
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